

**Contributing to SDG4 by programming with a University Social Responsibility Approach
Enhanced Access to Higher Education through International, Joint, Online and Hybrid Models**

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Abstract

International, joint, online and hybrid or Collaborative Online International Learning educational models are not new in Higher Education, however innovative programming that blends features from these models, and the growing on-demand factor in education started to gain visibility only recently. Spurring from Kyoto University's experience in international cooperation, its commitment to University Social Responsibility, and drawing from the demands posed on educational systems by the COVID-19 pandemic, this study aims to (a) identify the features that define each model, and (b) propose a framework of analysis that reveals how each model contributes to the achievement of individual targets in SDG4. First, based on the analysis of representative programs from universities around the world, the study identifies key features that define each educational model as international, joint, online, and hybrid through a qualitative comparison. Then, a quantitative approach is used to estimate how each model contributes to the attainment of every target in SDG4. The study provides a unique approach to enhance instructional design for universities seeking to boost their social impact and to improve accessibility to their academic programs to wider audiences.

Keywords

Higher Education, International Programs, Online Programs, Hybrid Programs, SDG4, University Social Responsibility

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Introduction

Starting from the assumption that education is a fundamental and enabling human right that empowers individuals and brings positive social development, the study builds on the notion that universities have a social responsibility that exceeds academia (education and research). As the SDGs gained consensus, universities too have become increasingly aware of their own social roles, having to reconsider their missions and how their social impacts align and contribute to the achievement of the SDGs (Mori, Fien, Horne. 2019).

International academic cooperation has a long history shaped by agreements and exchanges aiming to boost students' and researchers' exposure, creativity, and innovation, as a way to expand learning opportunities and access to them. Within this context, international, joint, online and hybrid educational models are not new phenomena in Higher Education (HE), this study, however, focuses on contemporary programming, the way academic models are envisioned and executed, their goals, the main stakeholders and their interactions, the outcomes these models produce, and particularly possible ways in which they can be combined into new learning opportunities, especially after the outbreak of the Covid-19.

This study is the result of an initiative that aimed to improve access to educational programs of Kyoto University in the context of the pandemic, and as a follow-up to a joint international Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) produced in cooperation with the University Social Responsibility Network, or USRN (Palacio, Sadehvandi, 2022). Building on this experience, the study seeks to identify defining features in international, joint, online and hybrid education as a way to further consolidate universities' commitment to social responsibility and to ensure access to quality education.

The study offers a framework to facilitate understanding of how universities can enhance content creation and accessibility of their programs in response to the protocols implemented as the pandemic unfolded in 2020 and 2021. While at the same time, the study addresses the issue of how universities create conditions that are conducive to achieving SDG4 in terms of offering quality education that is increasingly accessible, inclusive and that promotes lifelong learning opportunities.

The SDGs have motivated educational policy reform and innovative pedagogy development in HE in recent decades (Heleta, Bagus. 2021), while universities are called to provide vocational and technical means for people to access decent work and to become positive members of a global citizenship (Ferguson, Roofe. 2020). The following pages focus on the key aspects of how through international, joint, online and hybrid educational programs universities create conditions for a more inclusive educational landscape that can better contribute to the achievement of SDG4 by ensuring that programs promote equity, inclusion and gender equality.

The use of Information and Communications Technologies (ICT) eased the creation of new joint and distant learning environments that can motivate learners to build new skills (Alshabandar, et al, 2020). For example, Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) and other forms of e-learning are believed to democratize access to HE since they allow wider number of learners (Wulf, et al, 2014), and because they show evidence of their potential to enhance accessibility to quality education as compared to traditional learning (Ponnampalam, et al, 2019).

The sense of emergency brought by the pandemic exposed how wide the levels of preparedness were among countries and universities, and in spite of the initial shock, it became clear that universities would have to establish permanent and ad hoc mechanisms to support and boost continued education, staff development in technical aspects, and pedagogical advancements to be able to function in this new scenario. Even when major changes were already happening prior to 2019 in the promotion of online and hybrid education, COVID-19 prompted the conditions for a full-on shift to a digital dimension.

Based on these experiences this study aims to (a) identify the key features that define each model, and (b) propose a framework of analysis that reveals how each model contributes to the achievement of SDG4 and its targets from the perspective of higher education.

Literature Review

The literature suggests that although abundant research describes what international, joint, online, and hybrid programs are, there is still a need to understand how these models relate to each other, how accessible they are, and more importantly how they contribute to achieving SDG4. In other words, some level of comparison of how these models help universities bring their education to wider communities, and a better understanding of how these models can best contribute towards the achievement of each of the targets set for SDG4 appear to be missing, and these are the gaps this study aims to cover.

Online education historically suffered from lack of trust from academics, governments, employers, and learners, however the last couple of decades have shown growing levels of confidence particularly due to the development and massification of ICT. A trend observable both in the growing amounts of programs available and the growing expectations in their efficacy by providers, quality assurance agencies, and consumers (Romero-Gutierrez, et al, 2016).

In spite of having to provide remote learning opportunities that are accessible to wider audiences, ensuring high quality, needing well-prepared teachers, sufficient technical support, well-designed curricula, and investment in infrastructure, universities have adapted and promoted access to more and better programs, through tackling legal or administrative restrictions and by boosting investment in technology (Central Council for Education, 2014). By fostering online education, universities promote a cultural change that implies wider bridges with society, facilitating access to the education they provide (Sanoni, Palacio 2022). The pandemic contributed to this shift as previous distrust by governments, universities and the public had to come to terms with remote learning and the use of digital technologies (Mehla, Sheorey, Tiwari, Behl, 2021).

Even if the scope and nature of international, joint, online, and hybrid programs vary depending on the combination of elements such as level -undergraduate or graduate-, purpose -for degree or not for degree-, and financing -payed or for free-, these models share aspects like the issuance of certificates to evidence participation and achievements granted to learners (Knight, Lee, 2012).

Among the specificities of each case, joint academic programs, for example, are aimed to address the needs of students with specific career goals and with strong interests in two or more disciplines, which has given a boost to interdisciplinary cooperation (Michael, Balraj, 2003). These programs may be offered by a single university or by partnerships by several Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), sometimes located abroad. The growth in opportunities is clear, particularly since the late eighties, but there also exist challenges like quality

assurance, securing financial resources, legal restrictions, cyber security, inclusion and access to academic and technical resources by instructors and students (Girotti, 2010). Other issues include legal recognition by states of different diplomas; whereby acceptance of degrees and licensing continues to be largely dispersed (Bamford, 2020).

Theoretical approach

The study builds on the idea that universities have taken a leap by providing international, joint, online, and hybrid programs to address new demands from students and employers because these models enhance accessibility to wider communities; thus enhancing their civic engagement.

Due to their features, programs in each model address the underlying principles enshrined in SDG4, namely, creating the conditions to enhance gender equality and to foster access to education for all, promoting mutual understanding, tolerance, friendship and peace and promoting programming that provides technical knowledge and means to enhance the full development of the human personality. These educational models also advance the notion of education as a public good, where even if the state is the main duty bearer, other organizations too, have a role to play and contributions to make, as in the case of universities.

When considering the strategies universities use to enhance their agency for social change, connections to SDG4 are typically perceived as self-evident, however proper understanding of how programming in HE through these models really contributes to each of the targets in this particular goal remains unclear. Thus, this study aims to show that universities can have more meaningful social impacts by making their educational offer more accessible not only through the use of ICT, but also through the creation of relevant partnerships, while keeping up with demands for excellence in academic output. By better understanding each model, universities can enhance their academic portfolio and make use of creative channels to increase access to communities inside and outside their campuses.

Method

The study was done in two steps, first identifying key aspects of each model aiming to improve programming, and then developing a criteria to weigh how these models contribute to achieving SDG4.

The first step constitutes a qualitative account of the key programming features that define academic programs as *international, joint, online, or hybrid*. To this end primary data was gathered from websites describing international, joint, online, hybrid or COIL (Collaborative Online International Learning) programs presented as flagship by universities to create a broad picture of programs within each model, and a more focused search into descriptions of each model by previous researchers was done through academic search engines like Google Scholar, to gain more comparative depth.

A purposive sample was built with representative programs selected from universities with higher ratings in the THE and QS rankings, resulting in a sample of 9 international programs, 6 joint programs, 7 online programs, 3 hybrid programs that combine all three kinds -international, joint and online-, 7 COIL programs, and 3 service-learning programs with virtual mobility. Data was collected from September 2020 through June 2021.

Once data was consolidated, contents and thematic analyses were used to identify features of each model. The results of this analysis present first shared and common characteristics of the models, and then contrasting features are introduced in Table 1: *Defining features of each model*, where, in order to facilitate comparison, features are grouped and classified into the categories of: Origins and historical visibility, Goals of each model, Nature of partnerships, Course and credit recognition after mobility, Location, Implementation, Certification yield, and Challenges. Lastly a small number of representative programs from each model are presented for reference.

Based on the individual features spotted in the section above, the next step in the study is to estimate how each model individually contributes to the attainment of SDG4. To do it, a set of six indicators was created to gauge the relative degree in which each model contributes to every target of SDG4.

The indicators are defined as follows:

- **Well-trained educators & relevant contents:** referring to how each model contributes to increasing the number of individuals with access to quality education and training opportunities, increasing number of learning opportunities in diverse subjects, disciplines, skill development, Technical Vocational Education and Training
- **Accessibility & affordability:** referring to how each model increases access to wider audiences due to simplified procedures, alternative modalities, ICT use, flexibility for working learners, diversity of levels, lifelong education, increasing opportunities due to reduced costs of implementation, and number of free courses
- **Equality & distribution of learning resources:** referring to how each models contribute to the creation of policy and mechanisms to promote inclusion based on gender and minorities learning methodologies, improved geographical accessibility to learning opportunities, assignment of funds locally distributed, urban, rural and disadvantage areas
- **Institutional cooperation & social innovation:** referring to how each model promotes engagements, social interaction within and outside learning communities, complementary approaches (thematic and methodological), new ideas and synergies to address social and environmental problems
- **Effective learning environments:** referring to how each model contributes to the creation of safe places, facilities and infrastructure that address the needs for people with disabilities, gender sensitive and inclusive approaches to policy making
- **Contribution to peace:** referring to how each model promotes empathy due to international exposure, and to courses based on education for development, human rights, gender equality, and global citizenship

In order to appraise how each model contributes to the indicators above, a rating scale was created to quantitatively gauge the potential contribution of each model to the SDG4 target, focusing on the main beneficiaries of each of its targets. The scale is an abstraction consisting of an increasing set of values, where 0 (zero, presented as “-”) indicates that the model analyzed has no perceived or known contribution towards the achievement of a given SDG4 target; while on the other end, 3 (three) represents the highest potential degree of contribution towards achievement a model can have on each target. Values assigned to each degree of contribution are described as follows:

Degree: Meaning of value defined as contribution to achieving SDG4 target

- No perceived or known contribution in the achievement of this target
- 1 Minimal or indirect contribution in the achievement of this target
- 2 Intermediate contribution in the achievement of this target
- 3 High contribution in the achievement of this target

In order to allocate the values above to reveal the potential contribution of each model to each of the targets, Table 2: *Relative contribution from each model to every SDG4 target* presents every target -as a complete row, indicating also the main beneficiaries-, the indicators presented above are listed in the column to the left, while the values assigned as degree of potential contribution to each model are presented in following columns to the right in the following order International Programs (IP), Joint Programs (JP), Online Programs (OP), and Hybrid Programs (HP).

Finally, in order to apprise the relative contribution of each model to every SDG4 target, the values above are tabulated both horizontally (resulting outcomes: *total per target* on the last column to the right) showing the most sensitive targets to each model and hence a relative estimation of how effective these programs are in their contribution to the achievement of each SDG4 target. When figures are observed vertically (resulting in outcomes: *total per program*, at the center and right side of the table), the row at the bottom showing which of these models have more relative potential to contribute to the attainment of SDG4 overall. The final sum of both totals (*total per target* -right most column- and *total per program* -bottom most row) offers an overall idea of which of the indicators (as a form of contribution) are most sensitive to the models combined.

Results

1) Overview and key features of the four models

These educational models are envisioned by academics and university managers as a strategy of widen curricular opportunities, thus programs in any of these models aim to boost the contributions universities make to their learning communities through improved contents and diverse channels.

These programs are the result of academic cooperation from partners seeking to complement each other's educational resources and expertise, based on each other's strengths and capabilities. These efforts materialize through formal or informal arrangements, as preexisting or as ad hoc schemes in the format of Memoranda of Understanding (MOUs) or Student Exchange Agreements (SEAs) that serve as a common operational base.

International Programs (IP), Joint Programs (JP), Online Programs (OP), and Hybrid Programs (HP) exist in all levels of higher education – as pre-graduate, undergraduate, graduate and postgraduate, including PhD and postdoc levels-, and they promote mobility as a form of enhanced learning, which can happen both vertically, e.g., when students from a bachelor program move upward to a master's or PhD program within the same or to another institution; and horizontally when moving happens among different institutions in the same or different academic levels.

Although it is difficult to say which level of higher education offers the largest amount of IP, JP, ON, and HP, because they vary widely depending on the field of study and the countries involved, it is generally believed that these programs may be more common at the graduate level, as these students are often looking for more

specialized and advanced training in their field. In the sample created for this study more than 60% of programs analyzed operate at the master's level, mainly due to higher levels of compatibility, larger resources for research, easier administrative burden by enlisting more mature and independent students. It is also noticeable that the rapid development of online education is opening the doors to address the growing demand for continued education and lifelong learning among adults and already working people.

Programs can function as unilateral efforts from individual institutions, they can be the outcome from joint institutional endeavors, hence resulting in bilateral or multilateral agreements. When focusing on horizontal mobility and depending on the direction of people on the move they are typically classified as outbound, inbound, bidirectional and multidirectional, and they offer mechanisms for credit transfer and recognition of coursework completed, although these tools may vary widely, depending on the institutions involved and the specific program.

The duration of these programs varies but can be designed as fixed or flexible terms, lasting from a one-day activity, weeks, months, a whole semester, or even years. Typically they offer systematic instruction although with diverse forms, e.g. through lectures or seminars, guided fieldwork, discussion sessions and the like, whereby learning guidance happens from the institution towards the learners but may also include instances of mutual learning and development.

Upon completion, these programs yield certifications for learners who fulfill the academic expectations. Accreditations differ depending on the nature of programs and institutions, grading policy, student assessments, or evaluation of learning outcomes. Variations also relate to the number of certificates issued, how institutions grant them, whether they are single or multiple diplomas, or if they are issued by a single or multiple institutions. These credentials are the result of interactions and compliance with legal and academic requirements from various Quality Assurance (QA) agencies and systems like national regulations or frameworks.

As these programs aim to boost the encounter of people with different ideas and experiences, they promote cultural exchanges, mutual understanding, personal and professional development, and other interactions with and among students and faculty from diverse backgrounds. Students and researchers engage in collaborative, cross-cultural and trans-disciplinary activities within and outside formal programs to promote global competence, 21st Century Skills, and hands-on experience.

Programs in all these models share operational characteristics such as formalities and admissions requirements, like certifications of previous learning or language proficiency. Typically, they offer access to academic and non-academic resources to gear successful experiences among the learners, including e.g. support services, tutoring, advising, or career services.

All models face common difficulties such as the pedagogical challenges to ensure quality of education, ensuring wide and democratic accessibility to the communities they serve, sustaining the programs overtime and securing both personal and institutional commitments to upkeep financial, human, technical resources and partnerships, mutual support, close follow up with learners to reduce dropouts and participants being left behind. Language barriers may limit the quality of learning and cause troubles in administrative procedures. Credit transfer and recognition of certificates may be thorny due to academic or legal differences among partners, home and host countries. When physical mobility is required, programs may become expensive and logistically

challenging. Other challenges include compatibility of academic calendars and definitions of key terms among others. Table 1, hereunder, introduces the four models in parallel to highlight the key features that define each of them.

Table 1: Defining features of each model

Int'l Programs (IP)	Joint Programs (JP)	Online Programs (OP)	Hybrid Programs (HP)
Origins and historical visibility			
Traceable to the origins of HE and related to exposure as a booster for creativity	Since 1970's related to globalization and growing cooperative approaches to HE	Since 1990's with the growth of the Internet and cheaper ITC. Boosted credibility due to the pandemic	From the 2000's, combined features from IP, JP, OP, added to the use of ICT with actual mobility
Goals of each model			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HEIs unilaterally seek to broaden academic opportunities - Exposure is essential, cross cultural activities are embedded as curricular and non curricular - Internationalization abroad and at home - Campuses in tandem with global standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HEIs jointly seek to broaden academic opportunities - Conceived as concerted plans of action, benefits and burdens are shared from the start - Coordinated and complementary opportunities with easy access to programs and mobility in different HEIs - Conformity with legal, academic requirements of home and host countries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HEIs seek to broaden access to contents and programs to learners regardless of location - Enhanced learning through enriched access to quality education, flexible time through the use of ICT - Academic designers, and users benefit from lower costs as physical mobility is removed, reducing financial, logistical, and legal burdens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sophisticated academic cooperation to jointly broaden options, combining distance learning with actual mobility - New pedagogical method through ICT with coordinated teaching in different countries - Blend contents based on existing curricula, with reduced costs - Conformity with legal, academic requirements of home and host countries
Nature of partnerships			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unilateral bridging from a HEI to its partners - Decision making mainly at sending HEIs - Benefits and burdens covered by home HEI and learners - Formal agreements among HEIs may or may not exist, tend to be lax and general 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bi or multilateral engagements - Decision making includes all partners - Agreements define shared responsibilities and distribution of resources -academic, financial, etc.- - Agreements include preventive conflict resolution clauses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Typically one HEI unilaterally reaches out to its target audience - Partnerships with MOOC providers and other organizations are possible - Benefits and burdens are shared by learners and the provider HEI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bi or multilateral engagements - All aspects of the programs are jointly decided by partners - Formal agreements with clear distribution of responsibilities, tasks, resources, and conflict resolution clauses

Int'l Programs (IP)	Joint Programs (JP)	Online Programs (OP)	Hybrid Programs (HP)
Course and credit recognition after mobility			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partners' reputation unilaterally assessed by sending HEI - Unilateral decision by home HEI on credit recognition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mutual recognition of reputation - Credit-bearing courses and achievements mutually recognized - Shared curricular development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unilateral decision by home HEI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Joint curricular development, teaching, evaluation, and supervision of theses and research - Credit-bearing courses and achievements mutually recognized
Location			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partners abroad - Academic activities in different countries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partners and activities may take place in same or different countries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Independent of geographical location of HEIs and learners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partners and activities in same or different countries
Implementation			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temporary exchanges with or without credit transfer typically as non-degree programs - Short study abroad, or research exchanges - International travel required - Extra academic issues (e.g. credit transfer) and non-academic procedures (e.g. visas or insurances) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exchanges with credit recognition organized as regular for-degree programs - Short study abroad, or research exchanges - International travel may be required - Students participate in activities of all partner HEIs in the scheme 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No mobility required - Sessions online, on and off campus - Contents are broken in modules accessible at any time facilitating customization - Lectures as pre-recorded modules with less real time interaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - International travel may be required before, during or after the course - Mix of in-person and online interactions - Similar to in-person courses, students and faculty meet online in real time, with pre set dates and durations
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learning management systems (LMS) serve as digital platforms to house courses and offer communication tools, e.g. messaging systems, forum or discussion rooms, chats 	
Certification yield			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Certifications granted by HEI offering the program - Graduation diploma - Participation certificate - Credit transfer and recognition certificate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Double, joint degrees - Single degree granted jointly by two or more HEIs - Multiple degrees in different fields granted by one HEI - Two or more degrees granted by two or more HEIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Certifications granted by the HEI offering the program - From participation all the way up to PhD and other post graduate degrees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Certifications jointly granted by the HEIs offering the program - From participation all the way up to PhD and other post graduate degrees - Double, joint degrees
Challenges			

Int'l Programs (IP)	Joint Programs (JP)	Online Programs (OP)	Hybrid Programs (HP)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thorny QA that needs students', academics' and administrators' attention - Student support to address logistics, academic and legal matters, lodging, transport, special academic advisers - Limited accessibility relate to costs, mobility, and risk - Equal access may be limited due to gender, nationality, or other factors - Academic and non-academic challenges to be addressed by learners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - QA based on mutual institutional trust may lead to stratification of programs among HEIs that perceive each other in a similar tier of prestige - Management, coordination, and evaluation are more intertwined, with possible duplication or repetition of contents and administrative tasks - Limited accessibility relate to costs of programs - Demand to develop more systematic learning agreements - Equal access may be limited due to gender, nationality, background and other factors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure access to quality and safe ICT, to all members in the learning, teaching and support communities - Ensure digital literacy of all users, at all levels - QS credibility by academics, learners, governments, and employers - Growing need for technical know-how, support, and updating - Budget for specialized organizations in the structure of HEIs, IT personnel and infrastructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Same as OP - Ensure coordination and technical support, resulting in complex arrangements to distribute tasks and responsibilities - Agreement on academic credits, virtual examinations, and legal recognition of degrees prior and during operation - Effective and flexible communication - New costs for ICT, digital platforms, storage space, applications, affecting the distribution of logistic expenses - Although cheaper than IP, HP still expensive, hence inclusion remains limited

International, joint, online, and hybrid models offer creative paths to promote academic exchange by fostering quality education and research, while creating opportunities to make HE more accessible to wider audiences. These models boost mobility and exposure, they enhance for example, the establishment of international joint degree programs, the expansion of university networks and contacts with partners overseas, the production of MOOCs to attract learners from around the world, joint research, and enhancing support for international students.

When these educational models are observed based on their chronological appearance in the landscape of HE, it becomes clear that academic programming in HE has advanced and become more complex as designers strive to offer more relevant curricula and better solutions to larger communities, similarly as the Internet and other ITC's come into play programs in all four models become more accessible, affordable, safer, and inclusive. The developments observed in Table 1 on programming in universities demonstrate that HEIs now have a myriad of channels they can use to bring their academic work closer to new and expanding audiences.

When these academic models are included as part of the overall strategy for global engagement of a university -as compared to isolated initiatives by individual departments- they have better potential to deepen the effects of internationalization at home and expanding the opportunities for joint curricula development, and in so doing these models serve as strategies through which universities can enhance their contributions towards the achievement of SDG4.

In their own way, each of the four models promotes international exposure and connectivity among learners based on common interest to create new and extended communities. Given the nature of these programs, they

facilitate access to networks and meaningful engagement and interactions among researchers, enhancing dialogue and creating opportunities for mutual discovery, innovation and potentials for cooperation, for example, in joint research and funding.

From the four models analyzed, HP represents the most sophisticated and integrated version of them, with greater potential to boost quality, versatility, and accessibility to all learners. Due to their features, HP are expected to provide more productive interactional opportunities because individual students become more visible, hearable and accountable to educators and to one another, through reducing social loafing, while promoting meaningful social interactions and more shared interests (Bysouth, Ikeda, 2019).

Representative examples from each model

International Programs

- *Top Global Initiative: Japan Gateway*. Kyoto University
- *Alliance*. Columbia University, École Polytechnique, Sciences Po, Panthéon-Sorbonne University
- Multilateral mobility arrangements in Erasmus, UMAP, AIMS, Campus Asia

Joint Programs

- *Double, Joint degrees, Strategic Partnerships, On-site Labs*. Kyoto University
- *Online Joint/Dual/Double degree. Combined degree programs*. Syracuse University
- *Global Learning Initiative Program*. Association of East Asian Research Universities

Online Programs (OP)

- *MOOCs and free access to educational resources (OpenCourseWare)*. KyotoUx
- *Summer/Spring course 2021*. Kyoto University
- *Virtual English & Culture Course*. Monash University

Hybrid Programs

- *IARU: Joint Online Course. Focus: State Fragility and Peacemaking*. Cambridge, National University of Singapore, UC Berkeley, The University of Tokyo
- *3 European countries 1 joint PhD Diploma Online*: OUS Royal Academy of Economics and Technology (Switzerland), University of Dąbrowa Górnicza (Poland), Taras Shevchenko National University (Ukraine)
- *COIL: Going Beyond a Virtual Exchange in a Blended Mobility Project*. Kansai University, Fashion Institute of Technology
- *Comparative Research COIL Project on Peace*. Morito Institute, Hiroshima University

2) Relative contribution of each model to SDG4 targets

International, Joint, Online and Hybrid Programs as educational models in HE can contribute to the accomplishment of SDG4 in different ways and levels. These differences become more evident when cross-referencing the nature of each model analyzed in the previous section, with the main beneficiaries of every target in SDG4. Table 2, hereunder, brings together these aspects and offers a new framework of analysis to

better understand the options universities have when envisioning their programs, their partnerships, and the social contributions they wish to make.

Table 2: Relative contribution from each model to every SDG4 target

Indicator of potential contribution per SDG4 target	IP	JP	OP	HP	Total per indicator
Target 4.1: <i>Ensure that all girls and boys complete free, equitable, and quality primary and secondary education with relevant and effective learning outcomes</i> Main beneficiaries: children and young people					
Well-trained educators & relevant contents	1	2	3	3	9
Accessibility & affordability	-	1	3	3	7
Equality & distribution of learning resources	-	1	3	3	7
Institutional cooperation & social innovation	1	2	2	3	8
Effective learning environments	-	1	2	3	6
Contribution to peace	-	-	-	-	-
Total per model / <i>Global total</i>	2	7	13	15	74
Target 4.2: <i>Ensure that all girls and boys have access to quality early childhood development, care, and pre-primary education so that they are ready for primary education</i> Main beneficiaries: children and young people					
Well-trained educators & relevant contents	1	2	3	3	9
Accessibility & affordability	-	1	3	3	7
Equality & distribution of learning resources	-	1	3	3	7
Institutional cooperation & social innovation	1	3	2	3	9
Effective learning environments	-	2	2	2	7
Contribution to peace	-	-	-	-	-
Total per model / <i>Global total</i>	2	9	12	13	75
Target 4.3: <i>Equal access for women and men to affordable and quality technical, vocational, and tertiary education, including university</i> Main beneficiaries: women and men					
Well-trained educators & relevant contents	2	2	3	3	10
Accessibility & affordability	1	2	3	3	9
Equality & distribution of learning resources	-	2	3	3	8
Institutional cooperation & social innovation	2	2	2	3	9
Effective learning environments	-	2	3	3	8

Indicator of potential contribution per SDG4 target	IP	JP	OP	HP	Total per indicator
Contribution to peace	3	3	2	3	11
Total per model / <i>Global total</i>	8	13	16	18	110
Target 4.4: <i>Youth and adults with relevant skills, including technical and vocational skills, for employment, decent jobs, and entrepreneurship</i> Main beneficiaries: youth and adults					
Well-trained educators & relevant contents	-	2	3	3	8
Accessibility & affordability	-	1	3	3	7
Equality & distribution of learning resources	1	2	2	3	8
Institutional cooperation & social innovation	2	2	3	3	10
Effective learning environments	-	2	2	3	7
Contribution to peace	3	2	2	3	10
Total per model / <i>Global total</i>	6	11	15	18	100
Target 4.5: <i>Eliminate gender disparities in education, ensure equal access to all levels of education and training including persons with disabilities, indigenous peoples, children in vulnerable situations</i> Main beneficiaries: vulnerable individuals, persons with disabilities, indigenous peoples, children in vulnerable situations, women and girls facing gender-based barriers to education					
Well-trained educators & relevant contents	1	2	2	3	8
Accessibility & affordability	-	1	3	2	6
Equality & distribution of learning resources	-	2	2	3	7
Institutional cooperation & social innovation	2	2	2	3	9
Effective learning environments	1	2	2	3	8
Contribution to peace	3	3	2	3	11
Total per model / <i>Global total</i>	7	12	13	17	98
Target 4.6: <i>All youth and a substantial proportion of adults, men and women, achieve literacy and numeracy</i> Main beneficiaries: youth and adults with no or limited literacy and numeracy skills					
Well-trained educators & relevant contents	1	2	2	3	8
Accessibility & affordability	-	1	2	2	5
Equality & distribution of learning resources	-	2	2	2	6
Institutional cooperation & social innovation	1	2	3	3	9
Effective learning environments	-	1	2	3	6
Contribution to peace	2	2	2	3	9

Indicator of potential contribution per SDG4 target	IP	JP	OP	HP	Total per indicator
Total per model / <i>Global total</i>	4	10	13	16	86
Target 4.7: <i>Ensure that all learners acquire knowledge and skills for sustainable development</i> Main beneficiaries: All learners with knowledge and skills needed					
Well-trained educators & relevant contents	3	3	3	3	12
Accessibility & affordability	1	2	3	2	8
Equality & distribution of learning resources	1	2	2	2	7
Institutional cooperation & social innovation	2	3	2	3	10
Effective learning environments	2	2	3	3	10
Contribution to peace	3	3	3	3	12
Total per model / <i>Global total</i>	12	15	16	16	118
Target 4.a: <i>Education facilities that are child, disability, and gender sensitive and provide safe, non-violent, inclusive, and effective learning environments for all</i> Main beneficiaries: children and youth who can have access to facilities designed to meet their needs					
Well-trained educators & relevant contents	1	2	2	3	8
Accessibility & affordability	-	2	2	2	6
Equality & distribution of learning resources	1	2	2	2	7
Institutional cooperation & social innovation	2	2	2	3	9
Effective learning environments	-	2	3	2	8
Contribution to peace	3	2	2	3	10
Total per model / <i>Global total</i>	7	12	13	15	95
Target 4.b: <i>Expand scholarships available</i> Main beneficiaries: individuals who can access to scholarships					
Well-trained educators & relevant contents	1	2	3	3	9
Accessibility & affordability	1		3	2	8
Equality & distribution of learning resources	-	2	2	3	7
Institutional cooperation & social innovation	2	3	2	3	10
Effective learning environments	1	2	3	3	9
Contribution to peace	3	2	2	3	10
Total per model / <i>Global total</i>	8	13	15	17	106
Target 4.c: <i>Increase qualified teachers, including international cooperation for teacher training</i>					

Indicator of potential contribution per SDG4 target	IP	JP	OP	HP	Total per indicator
Main beneficiaries: children and young people, who can gain access to qualified teachers					
Well-trained educators & relevant contents	1	2	3	3	9
Accessibility & affordability	-	2	3	2	7
Equality & distribution of learning resources	-	2	3	3	8
Institutional cooperation & social innovation	2	3	2	3	10
Effective learning environments	1	2	2	3	8
Contribution to peace	3	2	2	3	10
Total per model / <i>Global total</i>	7	13	15	17	104

The educational models analyzed collectively scored the lowest in their potential for contribution to SDG4 in targets 1 and 2 (with respective global totals of 74 and 75 points). These low scores imply that programming in HE through these models can make relatively smaller marginal differences in the accomplishment of these targets, mainly because contributions are indirect as the beneficiaries of targets 1 and 2 are children and youth, while participants in the educational models analyzed are adults engaged in HE (tertiary or university). HP appears to have more potential to contribute to the accomplishment of both targets, 1 and 2, with 15 and 13 points respectively. Followed by OP with 13 and 12 points respectively. Indicators where these programs have more impact are *well-trained educators & relevant contents* and *institutional cooperation & social innovation*. According to this framework of analysis, these HE models seem to have low or no impact in terms of *contribution to peace*, which, again relates to the age of the main beneficiaries in targets 1 and 2.

In the case of target 3 -which aims to ensure equal access for women and men to affordable and quality technical, vocational, and tertiary education, including university- IP, JP, OP, and HP have a clear potential to contribute to achievement of this target, as compared to targets 1 and 2. The models collectively made a global total of 110 points, indicating promising space for action towards achievement of the target. This is explained due to both the nature of the programs in each model and the fact that main beneficiaries in target 3 are adults seeking to access affordable and quality education. Major contributions from the models are observed in the indicators of *well-trained educators & relevant contents* (10 points), and *contributions to peace* (11 points). Programs with more potential to make contributions are HP (18 points) and OP (16 points).

For target 4 -which aims to ensure that youth and adults can access relevant skills, technical and vocational skills, for employment, decent jobs, and entrepreneurship- these HE models have good potential to contribute towards achieving this target. Similar to target 3, there is a close correlation among beneficiaries of the target -young people and adults- and access to educational opportunities. Different from target 3, in target 4 the models offer more possibilities to contribute through the indicators of *institutional cooperation & social innovation* (10 points) and *contribution to peace* (10 points). Because of their nature HP (18 points) and OP (15 points) have more potential to contribute to the target as they enhance accessibility to education to larger communities.

When considering target 5 and the role HE has in eliminating gender and other disparities in education, these models reached a global total of 98 points, implying that they can make impactful differences by addressing the needs of the main beneficiaries in target 5 (vulnerable individuals) as these programs produce graduates, capable of producing policy and implementing it, hence having an expanding positive effects. Indicators showing more sensitivity to these models are *contribution to peace* (11 points) and *institutional cooperation & social innovation* (9 points). HP (17 points) and OP (13 points) offer the best chances to contribute to achieving this target.

Target 6 aims to increase literacy and numeracy among young people and adults, and potential contributions by the models seem more limited, compared to targets 4 and 5, with a global total of 86 points given that participation in courses provided in any of the models assume learners are highly proficient adults (capable of learning at university or tertiary levels). Graduates however do hold potential to create and implement relevant policy and other indirect contributions. HP (16 points) and OP (13 points) seem best suited to contribute to target 6, particularly through the indicators of *institutional cooperation & social innovation* (9 points) and *contribution to peace* (9 points).

Target 7 aims to ensure that all learners acquire relevant knowledge and skills to contribute to sustainable development, and because of the nature of these models, they offer the highest potential to contribute to this target. Target 7 obtained a global total of 118 points -the highest in Table 2- and comparatively speaking, points in all individual indicators are higher than in any other target. *Well-trained educators & relevant contents* (12 points), *contribution to peace* (12 points) and *institutional cooperation & social innovation* (10 points) are the indicators with highest scores, indicating areas where contributions have the best potential. At the program level, all four models offer higher contributions individually with HP and OP at the highest end (16 points each).

Targets 4.a, 4.b, and 4.c address mechanisms to boost access to HE and to boost the role of international cooperation and support for capacity-building, as such these HE models have strong potential to contribute to the achievement of these targets.

Target 4.a aims to foster the creation of educational facilities that are sensitive, safe, inclusive, and effective for learning, here the models obtained a global total of 95 points, whereby HP (15 points) and OP (13 points) show the best learning opportunities for educators and managers working on policy and implementation related to educational facilities, particularly in the indicators of *contribution to peace* (10 points) and *institutional cooperation & social innovation* (9 points).

Target 4.b aims to increase the number of scholarships with focus on enrollment in educational programs recognizing the role of HE in promoting economic and social development, and access to these opportunities. The models analyzed in the study represent the incarnation of how these scholarships can be utilized and key areas where HE can contribute to the achievement of SDG4. Collectively the models made a global total of 106 points -the second highest in Table 2-. HP (17 points) and OP (15 points) have bigger potentials, with contributions more evident in the indicators of *contribution to peace* and *institutional cooperation & social innovation* (with 10 points each).

Lastly, target 4.c aims to increase the supply of qualified teachers, hence when considering that most teachers obtain their training from HEIs, the correlation is clear. Programs within each model presented in the pages above can contribute to the empowerment of teachers and learners in many ways. The global total of points in

this target is also particularly high, with 104 points, implying great potential for contributions to the achievement of this target. HP (17 points) and OP (15 points) represent the most effective and accessible forms of education to which teachers and educators can access. While the indicators where these programs can contribute the most for this target are *institutional cooperation & social innovation* and *contribution to peace* (each with 10 points).

Conclusions

The study is a response to the challenges faced by universities in the strive to bring their programs to larger audiences in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic; it contributes to the understanding of programming in HE, and it offers an overview of how international, joint, online, and hybrid programs contribute to attain SDG4. The study serves as a starting point to consider the needs, roles and capabilities of universities to create, consolidate, or expand their academic and social roles.

COVID-19 was doubtlessly a major calamity with global disruptions, but it triggered new practices and developed a new culture in HE, not only as it boosted the use of ICT, but it also pushed for major innovations to face and overcome challenges such as the social distance protocols in ways that have rendered the whole HE sector more accessible, more inclusive, and more sustainable.

The study first analyzed examples of international, joint, online, and hybrid programs to spot defining features in each model and to consider ways in which they may be integrated as a strategy for universities to enhance accessibility. And then, based on the findings of that first step, the study moves on to reveal the relative weight these models have as universities engage with the challenges of addressing SDG4 and its targets.

The empirical observation of how these models function individually, provides a roadmap for action based on key areas of decisions that need to be made at the time of consolidating existing programs, adapting to new conditions or creating new ones that combine all types in cooperation with partners within and outside campus.

The study opens a door for future research related to innovative design of programming in HE, and to the elements and nature of cooperative relations in academia. Further research may deepen the analysis of measurable similarities and differences, as well as the potential of these models to improve decision making among academic designers and managers. The study also calls for more research on ways to measure and leverage academic cooperation in HE to contribute to the attainment of not only SDG4 but all SDGs.

Lastly and beyond research, it may be expected that innovative design and implementation of pilot programs that integrate the best features noted above may come into play; particularly in views of how international, joint, online, and hybrid programs focus and mingle with programming for service-learning as a way to promote university social responsibility.

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